

EDİTÖRE MEKTUP

LETTER TO EDITOR

PEDIATRIC TRAUMA: ASSESSING CHALLENGES AND IMPLEMENTING PREVENTIVE MEASURES

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ABSTRACT

Pediatric trauma, often stemming from preventable factors like traffic accidents, poses a significant health risk for children. Despite thoracic traumas being less common in children, they can range from mild to severe outcomes.

Traffic accidents, a leading cause of pediatric trauma, underscore the need for enhanced safety measures. The presence of thoracic injuries increases morbidity and mortality risks, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive evaluations.

Pediatric trauma scores (e.g., TRISS, PRISM, PIM, PTS) offer objective assessments, aiding in severity determination and treatment planning. TRISS, for instance, helps gauge trauma severity and risk, contributing to standardized management.

Incorporating these scores into clinical practice enables precise treatment plans and efficient patient monitoring. The overall approach involves developing safety measures, promoting protective equipment use, and raising awareness, with physicians actively implementing preventive measures for enhanced safety in pediatric trauma cases.

Keywords: *pediatric trauma, child health, trauma scores, TRISS, PRISM, PIM, PTS, traffic accidents, thoracic trauma, treatment plan, safety measures, protective equipment, preventive measures.*

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Dear Editor,

We read with great interest the article titled “Motorsiklet Kazasına Bağlı Çocukluk Çağı Toraks Travması; Vaka Takdimi” prepared by Başoğul et al., published in the first issue of your journal in 2023 (1). Congratulations to the authors and editorial board. However, we would like to touch upon a few issues to contribute to the discussion of the article.

Pediatric trauma stands as a significant health concern threatening the well-being of children and is a commonly encountered situation in emergency departments. Especially in developing countries, trauma ranks first among the causes of childhood mortality (2,3). This situation often arises from preventable factors, such as traffic accidents.

Children are more vulnerable to traumatic events compared to adults. Although skeletal system injuries are more frequently observed in this age group, thoracic traumas are generally less common in childhood. However, they can have a wide range of effects, from a simple injury to fatal outcomes (4). Particularly, traffic accidents stand out as one of the most common causes of traumatic injuries in children. The preventable nature of such accidents in children emphasizes the importance of measures to enhance traffic safety. The high mortality rates associated with motor vehicle accidents underscore the necessity for stricter regulations and protective measures in this field (5,6).

In cases of pediatric trauma, the presence of thoracic injuries can increase the morbidity and mortality risk for the patient. The flexibility and compressibility of the thoracic cavity in children, compared to adults, mean that even non-apparent injuries from the outside can lead to severe internal injuries (7). Therefore, when evaluating trauma in children, it is crucial to look beyond externally visible injuries (8).

Pediatric trauma is a common emergency in children that requires prompt evaluation, communication, and treatment (9). Objective determination of the severity of trauma plays a crucial role in clinical decision-making, and for this purpose, various trauma scores have been developed. These scores are measurement tools used to assess the post-traumatic condition of pediatric patients, guide treatment, and predict clinical outcomes (10-12).

Pediatric Trauma Scores:

TRISS (Trauma and Injury Severity Score): TRISS is a score used to determine trauma severity and morbidity-mortality risk. It is calculated based on age, gender, Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score, and Abbreviated Injury Scale (AIS) scores.

PRISM (Pediatric Risk of Mortality): PRISM is used to assess the risk of morbidity and mortality in pediatric trauma cases. It includes both laboratory and clinical parameters.

PIM (Pediatric Index of Mortality): PIM is developed to determine mortality risk in children admitted to intensive care units. There are both general and trauma-specific versions.

PTS (Pediatric Trauma Score): PTS is a score used to assess trauma severity in children. It is calculated based on GCS, arterial blood pressure, and respiratory rate.

Role of Pediatric Trauma Scores in Clinical Practice:

Pediatric trauma scores provide an objective assessment of trauma severity in children and guide the clinical decision-making process. These scores are valuable in determining the

urgency of treatment, developing treatment plans, and assessing morbidity-mortality risk in clinical practice (11,12).

For instance, using the TRISS score for a pediatric trauma patient, the severity of trauma and the risk of morbidity and mortality can be determined (13). This information is critical in formulating a treatment plan and monitoring the patient effectively.

Pediatric trauma scores are powerful tools for assessing post-traumatic conditions and determining treatment strategies in children. Effectively utilizing these scores in clinical practice can contribute to better clinical outcomes for pediatric trauma patients (11,14). These scores encourage standardization in trauma management and play a crucial role in data collection and comparison in clinical research (12,15).

In conclusion, pediatric trauma represents a significant issue threatening children's health and encompasses several preventable factors. The development of traffic safety measures, promotion of protective equipment usage, and increased awareness of trauma in children can play a critical role in reducing morbidity and mortality in this field. Physicians, when assessing pediatric trauma cases in emergency departments and hospitals, should consider these unique circumstances and strive for the implementation of further preventive measures to enhance overall safety.

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